

Co-designing Citizen Social Science for Collective Action

#8.1

Exploitation, Dissemination and Communication Plan

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Cite as: Wissenbach, Kersti, Sandres, Ana, Bonhoure, Isabelle & Perelló, Josep (2020). CoActD8.1: Exploitation, Dissemination and Communication Plan. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6076569>

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The CoAct project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 873048

Date – March 26th, 2020

Dissemination level - Public

Responsible Partner – Global Innovation Gathering (GIG)

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Document History			
Version	Date	Contributor	Comments
1.0	28.02.2020	Ana Sandres (GIG)	First draft with structure and content
2.0	12.03.2020	Kersti Wissenbach (GIG)	Reviewing first draft and translating first draft into strategic approach
3.0	23.03.2020	Isabelle Bonhoure and Josep Perello (UB)	Input, changes and exploitation plan.
4.0	26.03.2020	Ana Sandres (GIG) and Kersti Wissenbach (GIG)	Finalisation

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List of abbreviations

EC European Commission

EU European Union

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ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
FARN	Fundación Ambiente y Recursos Naturales
FHP	Fachhochschule Potsdam
FSMC	Federació Salut Mental Catalunya
GA	Grant Agreement No. 873048 with the European Commission
GIG	Global Innovation Gathering e.V.
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OKF	Open Knowledge International
UB	Universitat de Barcelona
UNIVIE	Universität Wien
UNSAM	Universidad Nacional de General San Martín
WPs	Work Packages
ZSI	Zentrum für Soziale Innovation (Centre for Social Innovation)

1. Executive Summary

CoAct proposes a radically new participatory approach through “four wicked” social issues in which citizen groups act as co-researchers. The overall objective of CoAct is to develop and demonstrate the scientific relevance and social impact of Citizen Social Science, which is to date an underexplored area of citizen science.

This document constitutes deliverable 8.1, CoAct Exploitation, Dissemination and Communication Plan in the framework of Work Package 8 (WP8). The plan will ensure that all communication and dissemination needs as elaborated in the CoAct WPs, alongside with the respective exploitation activities can be addressed strategically. Therefore, this strategy plan will be rooted in, and act upon, CoAct’s ethical values whilst cross-linking to the project’s data management plan (once in place).

Considering the evolving characteristics of the project, the exploitation, dissemination and communication plan will be regularly reviewed and updated in order to ensure that its objectives are met.

The aim of the document is to

1. Support all consortium partners to make decisions rooting their communication and dissemination actions in the CoAct ethical foundation
2. Guide all consortium partners through the process of making strategic decisions when choosing channels and tools to communication to or with different target groups
3. Make accessible the visual identity to be used for all communication and dissemination materials
4. Provide easy access templates
5. Share R&I strategies as they evolve

The CoAct project is funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Programme, through Grant Agreement No. 873048. The project will be active between January 2020 and December 2022.

2. Introduction

CoAct (Co-designing Citizen Social Science for Collective Action) proposes a radically new approach to face four “wicked” social global issues by engaging vulnerable citizens acting as co-researchers. The approach represents a new understanding of the underexplored field of Citizen Social Science, understood here as **participatory research co-designed and directly driven by citizen groups** sharing a social concern. An approach placing participation and agency of the citizen groups involved at its center also requires to translate such attributes for its communicative and dissemination activities. CoAct’s shared value set, consisting of Inclusiveness, Horizontality, Equity, Trust and Respect, Open Science, Co-ownership, Empowerment, and Reflexivity will thus underlie the direction we have taken in the direction and structure of this communication and dissemination strategy document.

This ambitious participatory approach, alongside the multitude and diversity of stakeholders being involved in communication and dissemination activities, as active stakeholders and passive receivers, does require coherent coordination when it comes to the activities being handled by the different coalition partners. Due to the multi-fold project design of CoAct, including concrete R&I Actions within the overall project framework, our communication and dissemination strategy will have to account for project level and tactics as well as tactics tailored towards the contexts and needs of the different R&I Actions.

CoAct’s overall mission is to deploy and demonstrate the scientific relevance and the social impact of Citizen Social Science, based on the three R&I Actions addressing Mental Health Care, Youth Employment, Environmental Justice and the Gender Equality Research Pilots. This implies a distinction between communication & dissemination activities serving the overall project communication and dissemination, and those activities concretely tailored within the R&I Actions.

2.1 Purpose and Scope of the Communication and Dissemination Plan

CoAct’s Project Management and Quality assurance Manual distinguishes between three forms of communication within the overall project, namely internal, external and towards the REA/EC. The CoAct communication and dissemination plan focuses on external communication, including internal operations

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enabling respective dissemination, outreach and engagement activities. External, here, does include tactics relating to all stakeholders not being official coalition partners. Thus, it comprises outreach and engagement tactics for and with actors, such as the citizen communities and Co-Researchers with whom we will collaborate, the Knowledge Coalitions we will form, etc.

The CoAct communication and dissemination plan addresses the **three target levels** of the project,

1. **Local R&I Actions** demonstrating the impact of Citizen Social Science
2. Developing a **Citizen Social Science approach** demonstrating its relevance
3. Shaping a **transnational Citizen Social Science community**

Figure 1. Target Levels for Communication and Dissemination

These three target levels address three different scopes

TL 1 is thematically and geographically bound

TL 2 is CoAct bound, transnational in its nature but otherwise framed

TL 3 is opening up beyond the R&I Actions and CoAct boundaries and communities

We can perceive all three as a cascading model, informing and cross-fertilizing each other.

The genealogical character of these three target levels implies that the communication and dissemination plan will be a living document, evolving alongside the unfolding of CoAct. Ensuring that evolving tactics are relevant to all its different contexts, this deliverable will serve as a guideline for the development of meaningful communication and dissemination tactics in the different scopes of these target layers, for CoAct overall and the concrete R&I Actions. Additionally, it will provide planning schemes for the meaningful and coordinated use of CoAct’s visual identity, as well

as CoAct’s own communication and dissemination channels and products serving to promote the overall project and engage relevant stakeholders.

WP8 is a cross-cutting WP that will coordinate communication and dissemination activities with all the other WPs in order to achieve the project's objectives. Project partners have defined eight general objectives for CoAct, striving to achieve and enable an understanding of Citizen Social Science valid as a framework for the execution of engaged social research (See Table 1). The main objectives underlying the project's communication and dissemination activities are objective 2, 7, and 8. Different communication and dissemination tactics will become relevant throughout the different target levels, in which coalition partners will have diverse responsibilities (See Figure 2).

Table 1. CoAct Objectives

Objective	Description
O1	To generate new ground-breaking and open scientific outcomes by means of Citizen Social Science
O2	To engage vulnerable citizens and local civil society groups in R&I initiatives and to place them at the centre of the R&I cycle
O3	To produce scientific evidence -informed reactions and thereby create new policies and to improve existing ones
O4	To build a common and validated transdisciplinary Citizen Social Science methodological framework for a variety of end -users
O5	To promote Open Science and scientific research integrity in methods and data
O6	To create and validate a robust and inclusive R&I evaluation framework
O7	To increase scientific literacy, skills, competences and public awareness regarding science
O8	To disseminate CoAct results and build a global sustainable Citizen Social Science community of Practice

Figure 2. Target Levels and Objectives for Communication and Dissemination

The plan will build on the ethical framework underlying CoAct by establishing guiding principles for all communication and dissemination related decisions to be made, thus addressing all WPs. Accounting for the promises made in the project proposal, in regards to communication channels and tools, this document will, then, reverse engineer a strategic guideline that supports all coalition partners to align communication and dissemination activities with the projects overall and its R&I Actions specific objectives. Overall strategy design will be distinguished from the communication and dissemination activities within the distinct R&I Actions, whereas R&I tactics will also be supported on the projects overall communication and dissemination level, contributing to target levels 1 and 2 (See figure 2). Doing so, tactics and deriving communication tools and channels can be realigned to dedicated target groups, foregrounding the different contexts we will be dealing with.

Therefore, this communication and dissemination plan will constitute a **modular document** providing

Foundational modules

1. **Normative framework** of all strategic decisions to be made
2. **Strategy Design Guideline** supporting all consortium partners to align decisions on their communication and dissemination practices and materials for and with different stakeholders with their concrete objectives

3. **Visual Identity** for all communication and dissemination materials
4. **Dissemination of results plan (Media planning templates)**

Evolving modules

1. Dedicated tactics to be developed in order to address the communication and dissemination activities underlying the eight WPs of CoAct
2. R&I Action strategies
3. Dissemination materials supporting CoAct outreach activities

2.2 Timeline

CoAct will run for three years and is based on various milestones, which our communication and dissemination tactics will have to adhere to (See Figure 3). It is important to stress that certain communication tools, as well as communication and dissemination content, will co-evolve throughout the different phases of the project life cycle and within the eight WPs. Thus, we will use an iterative approach for the outreach and engagement activities and the dissemination of results.

Figure 3. Communication and Dissemination Timeline

Year 1 - The first year of CoAct will focus on the design and implementation of local and thematically bound R&I Actions alongside the assessment of the state of the art of Citizen Social Science. Attention will be on the co-developing communication and dissemination tactics assuring participatory and context-driven approaches within the different R&I Actions. The R&I Actions

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consortium partners will develop their strategies with the support of GIG. The tactical repertoire will range from local outreach and engagement activities in order to form Knowledge Coalitions, engage relevant stakeholders, and create awareness about the R&I Actions and respective developments. These steps will feed into the communication and dissemination tactics. CoAct will develop on overall project level, thus contributing to the shaping of target levels 2 and 3 (see Figure 3), raising awareness about the methodologies, shaping and disseminating the rationale for establishing a CSS framework and actively reaching and engaging potentially relevant external actors in order to grow a transnational CSS community.

GIG will support R&I Actions coalition partners to develop and roll out their strategies in line with our normative framework. Furthermore, GIG will coordinate the planning of contributions required for project level dissemination and communication activities within the other WPs, from the bottom-up and cross-cutting different WPs. A media planning scheme, a visual identity, and templates to be used in order to prepare respective materials and populate respective communication and dissemination channels will be provided.

Table 2. Communication and Dissemination Activities 2020

Exploitation, Dissemination and Communication Plan (WP8)
Visual Identity Manual (WP8)
Presentation and deliverable template (WP8)
Social media and website set up (WP8)
Supporting local partners with their communication and dissemination strategy (WP3, WP4, WP5)
Creation of content for CoAct Dissemination and Communication (e.g. flyers, brochures, videos and articles) (WP8)

Year 2 – In the second year, local outreach will continue by the partners. Contents will be produced, deriving from scoping studies and the outcomes of the R&I Actions in order to frame and grow a Citizen Social Science approach, positioning CoAct as a reference point in the field. Respective products will be distributed through multiple channels, tailored towards different target groups.

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Global outreach and engagement campaigns will be in full execution with the aim of starting to build and establish a CSS community of practice. We will make available different options for diverse groups to engage with CoAct through our website, social media and events. Already in the second year, the CoAct’s co-designed results will be disseminated, through the translation of lessons learned into respective methodological approaches (e.g. co-design framework). Initial approaches will be re-visited and adjusted on the basis of external feedback and co-evaluation processes.

Table 3. Communication and Dissemination Activities 2021

Creation of content for CoAct dissemination and communication (e.g. flyers, brochures, videos and articles) (WP8)
Social media management (WP8)
Website updates (WP8)
Hackatons/Datathons (WP3, WP4, WP5)
Open calls for research pilot (WP6)
Citizen Social Science Summer School PhD students (WP8)

Year 3 - The third year will continue to focus on establishing the CSS framework and to grow the community of practice alongside a sustainability strategy, migrating CoAct into a standalone CSS. Dissemination and exploitation of results will find prominent attention during these months, through dedicated tactics, including the creation and roll out of the Open Citizen Social Science toolkit and the provision of policy recommendation in appropriate formats and through dedicated channels.

Table 4. CoAct Communication and Dissemination Activities 2022

Creation of content for CoAct dissemination and communication (WP8)

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Social media management (WP8)
Website updates (WP8)
Hackatons/ Datathons (WP3, WP4, WP5)
Final conference preparation and realisation (WP8)
Dissemination of Open Citizen Social Science Toolkit (WP2)
Dissemination of Public Deliverables
Exploitation activities (WP8)

2.3 From deliverables to strategy

Fundamentally, CoAct aims to be embedded in its ethical framework and respond to its set of objectives. Communication and dissemination tactics will play a central role in those regards, cross-cutting the deliverables of all WPs. (See Figure 4).

Figure 4. Assemblage of WPs, objectives and deliverables

The CoAct project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 873048

The role and most suitable tactics, formats, and channels for communication and dissemination activities per project deliverable will have to be assessed together with the responsible coalition partners per WP. This process will be supported by GIG.

From what to how

The fundamental elements we will work with in order to strategically approach each deliverable, will be introduced and elaborated in **Module 2** (Normative framework). **Module 3** will provide guiding checklists for each WPs group to reassess their own communication and dissemination activities per deliverable through a strategy and ethics lens.

3. Module 1 – Normative Framework

CoAct set out on a journey driven by the principles of **participation and openness**. This normative framework will elaborate what this means for dissemination and communication practices and will translate those foundations into guiding principles for the development of the different dissemination and communication strategies cross-cutting CoAct's plan.

Communication, per definition, can be seen as a spectrum, ranging from the dissemination of information to dialogic, inclusive engagement in the process of shaping dissemination materials and respective tactics. The dissemination of information in the form of materials to convey CoAct activities and results constitutes one pillar of the communication and dissemination plan. However, it is important to clarify, that also those materials will be rooted wider communication strategies in order to be designed and shared in ways relevant to their respective target groups.

Informing people, through the dissemination of information, in context relevant and thus accessible ways, is also to be seen as one vital element of a wider communication strategy, if we think about activities such as informing people about ways to engage in collective change activities, about feeding back dynamics and outputs from co-creative events we organize as elements of a wider communication strategy, or if we capture certain findings in reports, blog posts, or academic papers, in order to carry our engaged activities to a wider, multi-dimensional or envisioned future community.

CoAct embarks on the journey of a co-evaluation process, which intends to co-create and deploy an approach that demonstrates the scientific relevance and the social impact of Citizen Social Science. Its approach is rooted in a participatory ideology, resulting in an action repertoire. A communication approach adhering to such normative framing needs to put a strong emphasis on a recognition of communication as a dialogic approach, moving far beyond the mere exercise of informing people. Such approach embraces the recognition that diverse target groups have different contexts and needs, which have to be addressed when informing as well as actively engaging them in different phases of the project. This impacts the tactical repertoire and the subsequent communication and dissemination tools and channels to be identified, selected, and developed in the program. Simultaneously, CoAct, as a project funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, has to clearly distinguish between the project’s communication activities and those activities enacting the dissemination of project results.

3.1 CoAct Communication and Dissemination principles

In order to align CoAct’s communication and dissemination activities with its normative ambitions, the following concepts will be guiding the strategic decision making for all tactics and materials to be developed.

Figure 5. Guiding Principles

Inclusion

We understand participation as an inclusive approach of putting our target groups at the center. For our communication and dissemination strategy, and subsequent activities, this implies to make

the concept of inclusion a foundational principle for all decisions made in regards to respective channels and messages. How to assure not only availability, but accessibility on all levels of our strategy will be a guiding question for decision-making.

Accounting for

- relevant languages (translations)
- accessible tone of voice and formats (different writing styles, easy language formats, etc.)
- relevant communication channels
- relevant engagement tools

Innovation

We understand innovation not as the latest or mostly hyped technologies nor as predominantly digital. Our understanding of innovation is rooted in which communication means and channels are truly relevant to and accessible by the target groups we wish to reach and engage, thus not only openly available but also accessible. Such an approach is particularly relevant where working with vulnerable and/or marginalised communities as we do in our dedicated projects.

Accounting for

- communication channels and tools accessible (vs only available) by the target groups
- communication channels and tools adhering to openness principles wherever possible
- communication channels and tools securing the safeguarding of vulnerable target groups

Contextualisation

Contextualisation strongly relates to the principles of participation and innovation as defined above. Context-driven and needs based approaches imply that communication choices, tactical, technological, etc. are always driven by the direct demands of the target groups we work with and by their diverse contexts. Those can be of capacity-related or cultural nature as to how to choose communication channels, means, and design contents. This can also, depending on the sensitivity of topics, depend on political etc. contexts, which might require particular attention to people's

safeguarding. The latter can have important implications for the communication channels we choose, the ways we engage civil society, etc.

Accounting for

- Placing a context analysis at the beginning of all strategy design activities
- Acknowledging and accounting for the diversity of our target groups on a case to case basis
- Decisions on channels, tools, messages and the needs and capacities of the diverse target groups are inseparably and need to be decided based on the distinct contexts
- Prioritizing safeguarding of people we wish to engage over exposure (also if this sometimes means to limit choices of channels and tools)

Those guiding principles are underlying the tactical choices regarding target groups, mediated activities, channels, tools, and messages when developing communication and dissemination strategies, addressing dedicated project objectives in the different WPs. In order to ensure inclusive dissemination and communication tactics, we will predominantly depend on cross-media strategies, preparing formats accessible by our different target groups and framed towards the relevancies for different audiences.

With such an approach to the strategy design we assure that the tactical repertoire is explicitly addressing our dedicated project objectives whilst adhering to CoAct's normative foundations.

3.2 CoAct Communication and Dissemination tactics

The European Commission explicitly requests the distinction between communication and dissemination of results. Strategically, addressing CoAct's objectives across the three target levels will require a range of communication and dissemination tactics served by a more granular definition of different communication and dissemination activities. We are providing an overview of tactics relating to both communication and dissemination fields which will support the disentanglement of the tactical repertoires being listed.

Communication - Communication, for CoAct, relates to all **outreach and engagement activities** aiming to achieve the projects objectives and those of the dedicated WPs. Outreach, here, includes all types of actions aiming to inform people about upcoming or ongoing activities, on overall CoAct and R&I Actions level, and to engage people, through the provision of mechanisms to interact, join, learn, etc. and raising awareness about them.

Dissemination of results - Dissemination of results will relate to making available produced outputs reporting on the activities and achievements of CoAct, overall and relating to dedicated WPs.

Consequently, communication and dissemination tactics will be relevant across all WPs and on local R&I Action as well as broader, national and transnational project level and the most relevant tools and channels will be decided upon for each context.

3.3 Approaching communication and dissemination strategically

We distinguish between communication related and dissemination related tactics (see section 3.2) utilizing internal communication and dissemination means, such as CoAct’s own website, social media channels, and print products to be produced, and external communication and dissemination channels, such as traditional media outlets, websites and social media channels of relevant community members, academic publications. Making strategic decisions, here, always relates to moving into the communication environments of the target groups we wish to reach or engage whilst being driven by our guiding principles regarding inclusion, innovation, and contextuality.

Taking such fundamental steps for meaningful strategy development in mind (See Figure 6), we will take the initial considerations as listed in the project proposal as point of departure. Acknowledging the envisioned results and key messages we will revisit the existing assemblages and provide a

guideline based on which we will transform those into strategic pathways, responding to the objectives by

- being rooted in our guiding principles
- identifying all relevant target groups and embracing their diversity
- through the identification of each target group’s relevant contexts
- identifying dissemination and communication tactics possible
- selecting dissemination and communication tools relevant to the different contexts

The following attributes are to be addressed through the four objective pillars

- To **engage** vulnerable citizens and local civil society groups in R&I initiatives and to place them at the centre of the R&I cycle
- To **increase** scientific literacy, skills, competences and public awareness regarding science
- To **disseminate** CoAct results and **build** a global sustainable Citizen Social Science community of Practice
- To produce scientific evidence -informed reactions and thereby create new policies and to improve existing ones.

3.4 Target groups as listed in the proposal, from local to global

CoAct will reach and actively engage a diversity of target groups on local, national, and transnational level in order to achieve its objectives within the different WPs. For the design of relevant strategies, those levels will not be seen in silos but primarily be aligned to concrete objectives achieved throughout the different WPs. This will also entail a re-evaluation of target groups, identifying concrete actors, potential adding of further target groups, and to add granularly in order to assure the ability to account for concrete contexts when identifying meaningful tactics and related communication and dissemination means.

1. **Vulnerable citizens** in relation to Mental Health Care (Barcelona), Youth Employment (Vienna), Environmental Justice (Buenos Aires) and Gender Equality (Berlin, Eastern European countries, pan-European scale)
2. **Civil Society** and in particular associations, NGOs, grassroots movements, activists, neighbours, and other local communities that are connected to the concerns previously listed.
3. **Local/Regional administrations** (public bodies) like city councils, public regional institutions, public organisations (for example Women's Office), that are building and implementing social policies.
4. **National institutions** (public bodies) such as Ministries (Health, Employment, Environment, Social Affairs, etc.) that are responsible of social policies on a national level.
5. **EU and worldwide Researchers** coming from a variety of disciplines (Citizen Science, Social Sciences, Social Innovation, Computational Science, Science and Technology Studies, Technopolitics, etc.).
6. **International networks/associations** related with the different concerns as for example, the European Federation of Associations of Families of people with mental illness (see LOI).
7. **EU policy makers**, that can further disseminate and promote the implementation of new or better bottom- up policies, as well as boost Citizen Social Science uptake.

Figure 7. Local and Global Dissemination Target Groups

3.4 Tools

Figure 8 assembles all channels and tools. Tools, here, being defined as dissemination and/or communication means to carry out a particular function. Our tools can serve multiple functions when appropriated for concrete tactics or used to transmit concrete messages.

Example: Organising, facilitating, and benefiting from a hackathon does require outreach, engagement, and dissemination activities through a multitude of channels, directed at the different target groups and their envisioned roles (participant, being informed about, learning from the results, etc.)

These tools, as identified throughout the project proposal, are to be seen as means to an end. Utilizing each of them in a meaningful manner requires planning respective tactics around them.

Figure 8. CoAct Communication and Dissemination Tools

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Tools	Academic and non academic conferences (self-hosting, contributing)	Hackatons	Datathons
	Workshops (self-hosting, contributing)	Summer School (self-hosting, contributing)	External events, other (e.g. science festival, local weeks of science) Exhibition
	(Predefined) Policy briefs Recommendations White Papers	Website (intern, extern)	Social Media platforms (intern, extern)
	Newsletter (intern, extern) Mailing list (intern, extern)	Open repositories external	Flyers Brochures
	Presentations	Micro-learning videos Digital storytelling format	Infographics (e.g. in different formats, e.g. collapsable cartographies)
	Scientific and non-scientific publications (different formats, open access)	Training materials (e.g. guidelines and toolkits)	Print media (e.g. newspapers)

Table 5. Predefined dissemination materials

Work Package	Special Deliverables
WP2	D2.5 Brief for policy makers: Opportunities and Challenges of Citizen Social Science
WP3	D3.3 Brief on policy recommendations and action plans to enhance recovery processes and Mental Health Care self-management
WP4	D4.4 Policy guidelines and models for new social measures on Youth Employment
WP5	D5.4 Policy brief on Environmental Justice: social perception of risks and model replicability in European contexts
WP6	D6.2 Gender Equality White Paper and bottom-up Research Pilots final report.
WP7	D7.3 White paper on co-evaluation of Citizen Social Science R&I
WP8	D8.4 Citizen Social Science Open Training Materials for social scientists PhD programmes

4. Module 2 - Guidelines: From values to strategic action

The communication and dissemination plan sets out to support a strategic approach for decision making within each WPs. In this way, we can make informed decisions, selecting and shaping our tools, channels, and messages tailored towards the context of the respective stakeholders whilst being rooted in our ethical framework.

We will build on the target groups, channels, and tools listed but provide a guideline that enables respective coalition partners, with dedicated support by GIG, to revisit those assemblages and

transform them into strategies, which are rooted in the guiding principles and, in their tactical repertoire, explicitly align with their respective objectives.

Figure 9. Communication and Dissemination Guidelines

STEP 1

4.1 Choose your pathways

1. R&I Actions > full communication and dissemination strategies
2. WPs coherency > Reverse engineering communication and dissemination tactics for deliverables to meet objectives
3. Concrete deliverables > Developing communication and dissemination tactics to make concrete tools meaningful to diverse target groups

Pathway 1 - R&I Actions > full communication and dissemination strategies

Driving question

1. What are the objectives we wish to achieve
2. Which target groups play a role in achieving each objective
3. How does each target group relate to achieving the respective objective? > which tactics relevant

4. What are the contexts of these target groups? > which means to enact relevant tactics

Example: Designing the R&I strategies in themselves coherent and rooted in the strategic process. Simultaneously accounting for feeding back to the vulnerable communities, and an inclusive list of stakeholders and deriving tactics, also at the levels of producing policy documents and tracking outcomes.

Pathway 2 - WPs coherency > Reverse engineering communication and dissemination tactics for deliverables to meet objectives

Driving Questions

1. How do the deliverables relate to the objectives?
2. Which functions do the deliverables have to fulfil in order to address the objectives?
3. Do we identify gaps?
4. Which target groups play a role?
5. Which roles do the different target groups have?
6. Which tactics would therefore be relevant in relation to each target group?
7. What are the target groups contexts?
8. Which tools are therefore meaningful in order to 'activate' the different target groups in achieving our objectives

In this step, we might identify gaps which might require a rethinking of certain deliverable formats or additional elements required in order to meaningfully create and enact those deliverables.

Pathway 3 - Concrete deliverables > Developing communication and dissemination tactics to make deliverables meaningful to diverse target groups

Driving Questions

#8.1 Exploitation, Dissemination and Communication Plan

1. What are our main aims with this product?
2. Which are the target groups relevant to achieve those aims?
3. What are the target groups roles in achieving our aims?
4. What are the contexts of each target group?
5. What would be relevant tactics regarding envisioned roles and the different contexts?
6. What would be meaningful tools (communication channels) per tactic if you take the contextual aspects for your different target groups into account?

Example: Which tactical steps do we need in order to assure our toolkit to reach the right target groups and enable engagement where relevant? Have we thought through all target groups and prepared our materials in respective formats, languages, etc?

If we wish to monitor reactions and feed them back into our community, to different target groups that have been involved, which tactics and channels are most meaningful?

Underlying lenses for all pathways

- Guiding principles
- Data Management Plan

STEP 2

Go through each question of your pathway and use the assigned checklists in order to make decisions.

4.2 Checklists

a) Purpose checklist

The table below provides an overview of objectives and deliverables. Those will be the points of departures of considerations for each pathway. Considering or re-assessing the correlations between objectives and deliverables or, as for pathway 3, revisiting the deliverables and assessing where concrete outreach and engagement strategies are required in order to put the deliverable at use, this is what the table will serve to start with.

Table 6. CoAct WPs, objectives and deliverables Overview

Work Package	Description objectives	Description Deliverables
WP1 Project Management and Coordination	Ensure the accomplishment of the project objectives on time, under budget and at the highest quality, and the maximization of the impact of the results.	-Project management and quality assurance manual -Data management plan
WP2 Citizen Social Science Foundations	O4. To build a common and validated transdisciplinary Citizen Social Science methodological framework for a variety of end users. O1. To generate new groundbreaking and open scientific outcomes by means of Citizen Social Science. O2. To engage vulnerable citizens and local civil society groups in R&I initiatives and to place them at the centre of the R&I cycle. O8. To disseminate CoAct! Results and build a global sustainable Citizen Social Science community of practice.	-Report on State of the Art of Citizen Social Science -Report on Capacity Building within the consortium -Report on Informed consent procedure requirements and challenges -Open Citizen Social Science Toolkit -Brief for policy makers: Opportunities and Challenges of Citizen Social Science
WP3 R&I Action #1: Mental Health Care, Barcelona	O1. To generate new ground-breaking and open scientific outcomes by means of Citizen Social Science. O2. To engage vulnerable citizens and local civil society local groups in R&I initiatives and to place them at the centre of the R&I cycle. O3. To produce scientific evidence -informed reactions and thereby create new policies and to improve existing ones. O7. To increase scientific literacy, skills, competences and public awareness regarding science	-Report on Knowledge Coalition building -Digital and non--digital tools for conducting research -Brief on policy recommendations and action plans to enhance recovery processes and Mental Health Care self--management
WP4 R&I Action #2: Youth Employment, Vienna	O2. To engage vulnerable citizens and local civil society groups in R&I initiatives and to place them at the centre of the R&I cycle. O3. To produce scientific evidence informed reactions and thereby create new policies and to improve existing ones. O7. To increase scientific literacy, skills, competences and public awareness regarding science. O1. To generate new ground-breaking and open scientific outcomes by means of Citizen Social Science.	-Report on Knowledge Coalition building -Inclusive Toolbox for Citizen Social Science -Policy guidelines and models for new social measures on Youth Employment

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<p>WP5</p> <p>R&I Action #3: Environmental Justice, Buenos Aires</p>	<p>O2. To engage vulnerable citizens and local civil society groups in R&I initiatives and to place them at the centre of the R&I cycle.</p> <p>O3. To produce scientific evidence informed reactions and thereby create new policies or to improve existing ones.</p> <p>O1. To generate new ground-breaking and open scientific outcomes by means of Citizen Social Science.</p> <p>O7. To increase scientific literacy, skills, competences and public awareness regarding science</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Report on Knowledge Coalition building -Collapsible cartographies -Open Source digital platform -Policy brief on Environmental Justice: social perception of risks and model replicability in European contexts
<p>WP6</p> <p>Endeavoring new Citizen Social Science Spaces – Gender Equality</p>	<p>O2. To engage vulnerable citizens and local civil society local groups in R&I initiatives and to place them at the centre of the R&I cycle.</p> <p>O5. To promote Open Science and scientific research integrity in methods and data.</p> <p>O1. To generate new ground-breaking and open scientific outcomes by means of Citizen Social Science.</p> <p>O3. To produce scientific evidence- informed reactions and thereby create new policies or to improve existing ones</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Open Calls resolution report -Gender Equality White Paper and bottom-up Research Pilots final report
<p>WP7</p> <p>Evaluation and Impact Assessment</p>	<p>O6. To create and validate a robust and inclusive evaluation framework.</p> <p>O5. To promote Open Science and scientific research integrity in methods and data.</p> <p>O1. To generate new ground-breaking and open scientific outcomes by means of Citizen Social Science</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Impact Assessment Plan -Interim Impact Assessment Report -White paper on co-evaluation of Citizen Social Science R&I -Final Impact Assessment Report
<p>WP8</p> <p>Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation</p>	<p>O8. To disseminate CoAct! results and build a global sustainable Citizen Social Science community of practice.</p> <p>O7. To increase scientific literacy, skills, competences and public awareness regarding science.</p> <p>O2. To engage vulnerable citizens and local civil society groups in R&I initiatives and to place then at the centre of the R&I cycle</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Plan for Exploitation, Dissemination and Communication -Visual Identity manual for offline and online materials -Interim Report on communication, dissemination and exploitation -Citizen Social Science Open Training Materials for social scientists PhD programme -Final Report on communication and dissemination -Exploitation plan

b) Target groups checklist

The target groups need to be elaborated further. However, in this step it would be about identifying concrete target groups per category in order to be able to assess relevant contexts etc. for each. Where possible, this would be up to the level of listing, for instance, concrete NGOs or activist groups, or public institutions, research institutes or research groups within institutions, etc.

Identifying detailed target groups goes hand in hand with the process of thinking through the role each of them would have in achieving your aim (See section 3.4 to have an overview of the target groups).

c) Target group roles checklist

Consider different forms of engagement when identifying what role each target group would play in your strategy or activity (See figure 10). Consider to give them respective names to work with. The engagement pyramid can help to think through the different roles a target group can have.

Figure 10. Engagement Pyramid

d) Checklist tactics

In order to get our target groups engaged to the extent required so they would fulfill the role we have envisioned, we have various options. Choices, here, should derive from the different contexts we identify per target group and from our guiding principles. This is important to ensure that our tactics will be meaningful.

e) Context Checklist

Ask yourself which contexts would speak for or rule out the use of certain tools/channels. We can think of different categories of contexts. Certain categories or aspects will be more relevant when working in particular geographic areas, remote versus urban, or with particular target groups.

Figure 11. Context Checklist

f) Tools checklist

The communication and dissemination means have been broadened as to provide a grid serving the identification of means to support the tactics supporting you to achieve your aim whilst accounting for the respective relevant target groups with their particular contexts. These tools are a combination of CoAct’s own dedicated products, such as the website, the toolkit, etc. and other

communication and dissemination means serving as standalone tools supporting your strategic means as well as those enabling the promotion, dissemination, etc. of our own products/platforms (See Figure 8 for an overview of the tools).

For a meaningful identification of the meaningful tools per tactics and respective target groups, consider to specify as much as possible. E.g. identify concrete external websites or social media sites you wish to share your message or product on. Identify concrete events or mailing lists in which you wish to trigger a conversation, etc.

Always re-check if those tools are truly the most relevant to the target groups you wish to address or engage, given their particular contexts. Also always consider if the tools you choose are the most relevant in order to execute the tactics they shall support, e.g. which tool is truly able to engage people, to people to actively share their stories, for policy makers to act upon our suggestions, etc.

When we talk about tools defined, as means to an end, in our case means to execute a certain tactics in a context relevant and inclusive manner, the shaping of the content those tools will carry is of equal relevance.

This relates to the tone of voice, the selection of languages, as well as the preparation of content in various formats, such as easy language formats. Those decisions need to be made explicit in your activity, tactics, or strategy design. Explicit, here, refers to decisions clearly rooted in the target groups and their contexts.

g) Guiding Principles Check

The guiding principles for all CoAct communication and dissemination related decisions and actions build the cross-cutting foundation for all decisions we make when working through any of the three pathways outlined in the guideline module.

1. Inclusion

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- Are the tools I am considering accessible for the respective target groups?
- Which languages do we need to translate what content into in order to reach or enable our envisioned target groups?
- What are the tones of voice appropriate to reach or engage our envisioned target groups?
- Do we need multiple formats in order to reach or engage our envisioned target groups?
- Do we need to develop different tools or formats for target groups in different localities?
- Do we put people at risk with our envisioned tactics and tools?
- How can we assure true consent for all our target groups (considering their abilities and our limits of control when it comes to certain platforms)
- Have we considered certain patterns of exclusion/silencing/other forms of stigmatisation when e.g. aiming at steering engagement on certain platforms?
- Are we engaging our own transnational civil society community for advice and action?
- etc.

2. Innovation

- Which are the most relevant formats in regard to my context groups' contexts?
- Do we have open and free source solutions for the tools we aim to use/build?
- Are we engaging existing expert communities in the issue we aim to address?
- Have we clearly considered our tools' accessibility for different target groups as distinct from availability?
- Are we moving into the communication environments of our target groups or expecting them to access new spaces/tools/platforms, etc.?
- Are we formulating clear calls for action/expectations for our target groups or putting things out there expecting something to happen?

- Have we prioritized the safeguarding of our different target groups over the trying out of new (digital) formats?
- Are we building on our own transnational communities (GIG, OKF) for respective advice?
- Are we building the tools of our own transnational communities (GIG, OKF) in order to assure safeguarding, meaningful innovation, and in order to avoid the replication of the wheel?
- etc.

3. Contextualisation

- Did we undergo an extensive assessment of different contextual aspects for each target group and have applied them to our tactics and tool decisions?
- Have we identified diversity within certain target groups and accounted accordingly?
- Have we taken the contexts of all such diversity within the target groups into account?
- Have we conducted a thorough safeguarding check, in regards to contexts and the agency over different channels we intend to use?
- Are we sure to prioritize the safeguarding of certain target groups over potential popular tools?
- etc.

5. Module 3 – Visual Identity

In order to assure recognition of all communication and dissemination channels and materials across all CoAct activities, we are introducing the visual identity of the project through the Deliverable 8.2 Visual Identity manual that will be sent as a separate document. The visual identity manual of CoAct comprises:

#8.1 Exploitation, Dissemination and Communication Plan

- Logo versions and guidelines on how to use it and when
- Symbol and how to use it
- Typography
- Colours schemes
- Deliverable Template
- PPT Template

Consortium partners will have to refer to the Visual Identity Manual to get the guidelines that will assist them on how to use CoAct brand in a clear and consistent way.

Logo

6. Media Planning - Project level

As part of CoAct's communication and dissemination strategy, we have developed an initial media plan for the two communication and dissemination tools that will be owned and managed by CoAct throughout the entire three years project period.

The CoAct's website and its dedicated social media accounts (Twitter, Facebook, and Instagram) will constitute the four central, structural dissemination and communication tools on overall project level.

Our understanding of inclusion, innovation, and contextualization (our guiding principles) translate into the ways we shape, communicate, and disseminate our messages through these channels.

- Content will be made available in English, Spanish, Catalan, and German

The CoAct project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 873048

- Project specific content will be made available in the languages of the project communities as priority. Translations into further languages will come as a subsequent step
- Dedicated sections of the website and further communication and dissemination products will be made available in different formats in order to foster accessibility, e.g. audio formants and easy read format. The tone of voice chosen for each communication and dissemination product will respond to the needs and communication cultures of the dedicated stakeholders and target groups. Messages will be adapted to the specific target group to ensure that the message resonates with their context and fosters their engagement.

Finally, to ensure a consistent flow of information and instrumentalisation of the tools for the objectives coordinated by each coalition partner, we are introducing a media plan for each channel.

6.1 Project Internal Communication Channels - Moderation and Responsibilities

a) Website

Why: Our CoAct website will be the main online channel for our communication and dissemination activities. The proposed domain of the website is www.coactproject.eu. The website will be designed and built to become user-friendly and will provide interested stakeholders the options and opportunities to engage with us.

Regarding its structure, the website version 1.0 has been initially structured to provide information about what is CoAct, who are the partners and advisory board members, an overview of the research and innovation actions and bottom-up research pilots as well as an overview of the resources that we would be creating and sharing on the website during the lifetime of CoAct. A dedicated section has also been created to include general information about what citizen social science is within the project and what is its current state.

Moreover, in order to have a centralised space for interested individuals, groups and/or organisations to find more information about the ways to engage with us and be part of a citizen social science community, the website will then share this information as well as cross-linking to other online communities and/or platforms around citizen social science that we can take part in.

Finally, a news and events section is included where news will cover for example latest publications, and where CoAct events and participation in events will be featured. The default language of the website will be initially English. Updates on the website, could translate e.g. into translating the website to German, Spanish and Catalan based on available resources to do so.

The project proposal suggests setting a blog on the website. To be able to do so, consortium partners will have to agree on different elements such as who would provide the posts, when, how often, etc. Answering these questions before setting a blog will ensure its sustainability and successful implementation.

Who: GIG would be the consortium partner in charge of writing the vast majority of the website contents, editing the contents written by the partners, monitoring the website activities, reporting on its statistical records, ensuring web-hosting support as well as updating the content, news and events. Related to the last responsibilities (updating news and events), GIG would however need the contribution from the consortium partners to ensure that GIG is covering and following the different activities/publications that are being carried out locally by the different partners.

Where: To collect and follow up on the activities/publications of consortium partners, the following templates have been created, which serve two purposes. On the one hand monitor the communication and dissemination activities against our KPIs, and the second one to be able to have an overview on these activities to ensure that GIG documents and shares all the relevant news and events.

- a) **Press and Media Outreach** - Partners will have a dedicated space within the template to input their communication and dissemination activities on the document, whether it is posting on their institutional social media accounts and/or website, newsletters, press releases, video posting, blogs, etc. (See Annex I)
- b) **Events template** - This template will differentiate between the events that consortium partners will be attending and the ones that will be organised by them around CoAct. (See Annex II)

When: Consortium partners will be expected to update the press and media outreach template at the end of every two weeks. Regarding the events template, if partners are organising events they have to include this information before the event happens so that we can also promote it through our social media and website event section.

b) Social Media

Why: Facebook, Twitter and Instagram constitute important online channels for CoAct, serving to reach and engage with the wider community of scientists, the general public and other stakeholders. All project partners will advertise the CoAct's social media accounts to their respective audiences in order to reach the highest possible follower numbers.

Who: GIG will manage the following social media CoAct accounts:

Figure 12. CoAct's Social Media Accounts

Considering that the local activities will feed the global communication and dissemination strategies, consortium partners will contribute and directly input the content that they want CoAct to share, whether it is related to activities, publications, etc.

Where: To collect the direct contributions and content input from consortium partners for our social media posts on Facebook and Twitter, the following template has been created:

- a) **Editorial Plan:** It's a template that will allow GIG to create and organise social media posts that will be collaboratively created by partners.

When: Consortium partners are expected to contribute with Tweets and Facebook and Instagram posts time they carry out activities/events around their work within CoAct (See Annex IV).

6.2 Mailing list and newsletters

The newsletters of the partners closer to civil society, like FSMC and FARN, will serve as a channel to communicate to a wider audience. Other grassroots movements and NGOs dealing with the social concerns explored in CoAct will be contacted in order to reach a potential interested audience. Furthermore, CoAct results and main events (call launching, summer school, final conference) will be disseminated through targeted emails and the newsletters of the main Citizen Science associations such as ECSA or CSA, as well as newsletters of partner organisations such as FSMC (+9.000 newsletters subscribers). These activities will follow our guiding principles (inclusion, innovation and contextualisation)

7. R&I Actions - Communication and Dissemination Strategies

The general objective of CoAct is to deploy and demonstrate the scientific relevance and the social impact of Citizen Social Science based on the R&I Actions addressing Mental Health Care in Barcelona, Youth Employment in Vienna, Environmental Justice in Buenos Aires, and Gender Equality in Europe. In order for each partner implementing an R&I Action to successfully communicate CoAct and disseminate the results, they will have to develop context driven strategies based on the guiding principles presented throughout this plan considering that each specific WP (WPs 3, 4 and 5 R&I Actions), the actors, the concern, the methodologies and the open tools will be different. As a first step towards partners developing their own local communication and dissemination strategies, they have worked on a first draft that will be revisited with them and GIG to help them translate the plan guidelines into practical ways.

8. Evaluation and monitoring of communication and dissemination activities

To monitor the effectiveness of our communication and dissemination activities, we will collect and monitor quantitative indicators and conduct qualitative measures from the target groups addressed or engaged in various capacities.

Adhering to our guiding principles of participation, innovation, and context, central attention will be given to engagement with our target groups in ways enabling their diverse needs and contexts being addressed, apart from quantitative KPI measurement.

8.1 Quantitative monitoring

Communication and dissemination activities will be carefully measured to ensure that its impact is maximized. Analytic tools are planned to be used to keep track of the number of visitors of the webpage and the number of downloads related the Open Social Citizen Science toolkit. Records of number of participants in CoAct events will be carefully documented and their impact on the participants will be evaluated in the frame of the evaluation WP7.

Note: Any considerations relating to the use of data deriving from any monitoring and evaluation methods will require a rigorous ethics screening that needs to be discussed with other consortium partners (UB, ZSI, OKF) on how this is envisioned in the ethical framework and the data handling policy. The same will apply to any considerations of using data, be it statistical data or public user contributions, such as comments or likes, from our online channels.

Table 7. Communication and dissemination monitoring

		M1-M12	M13-M24	M25-M36
Dissemination activities	Social media strategy	Twitter: 500 followers	Twitter: 1.500 followers	Twitter: 3-5K followers
	Digital distribution targeting consolidated platforms	Facebook: 500 followers Instagram: 100 followers	Facebook: 1.500 followers Instagram: 300 followers	Instagram: 500 followers
	CoAct Project Website	Web-stats: 200visits/month Av. Session: > 2 minutes	Web-stats: 300visits/month Av. Session: > 2 minutes	Web-stats: 500 visits/month Av. Session: > 2 minutes

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	CoAct Open Science Toolkit	--	Web-stats: 150 downloads	Web-stats: 950 downloads
	Scientific publications	1 research article	3 research articles	5 research articles
	National and International specialized events/year	3 presentations in Intl. congresses: 1,000 recipients	5 presentations in Intl. congresses: 1,500 recipients. 1 Datathon 1 Hackathon 3 open calls launching CSS summer school: 30 attendees	10 presentations in Intl. congresses: 1,500 recipients. 2 satellite workshops 1 Datathon 1 Hackathon Final conference: 150 attendees
	Online innovative materials (micro-learning videos, digital storytelling and infographics)	3 pieces	5 pieces	5 pieces
Communication activities	CoAct printed material distribution	Flyer: 600 recipients Infographic postcards: 1.500 recipients	Updated flyer: 1,200 recipients. Infographic postcards: 2,800 recipients	Brochure: 3,000 recipients. Infographic postcards: 3,500 recipients
	National and International public events/year	At least 4 public presentations	At least 6 public presentations	At least 10 public presentations

8.2 Qualitative monitoring

The evaluation and impact assessment of the strategies cross-cutting all WPs will be led by WP7 (ZSI). WP8, with the approach introduced in the communication and dissemination plan, works towards the acceleration of coherency between deliverables and objectives in the realms of communication and dissemination tactics. This approach aims to contribute to leverage impact respectively.

The role of the final communication and dissemination tactics in achieving the project's objective will need to be an integrated part of the overall mixed-methods evaluation framework. The collaboration of GIG with the lead coalition member of WP7 will therefore be required.

GIG will coordinate with WP7 leads in order to develop a holistic methodological framework accounting for the assessment of dissemination and communication activities in achieving the project's objectives.

9. Exploitation

This section presents the conceptual frame of Exploitation in CoAct and the internal foreseen activities, that will lead to the preparation of an Exploitation Plan (Deliverable D8.5) to be submitted at M35. Here, Exploitation is defined as under the Horizon 2020 Rules for Participation¹:

“Exploitation means the use of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.”

The exploitation activities are led by UB as a specific task in WP8 (T8.6 Exploitation Activities).

9.1 Conceptual frame

CoAct is strongly positioning itself in the frame of Open Science, meaning that it adheres to Budapest and Berlin Declarations on Open Access to Knowledge in the Sciences and Humanities and the Paris OER Declaration on Open Educational Resources.

Consequently all Educational Resources produced during the course of CoAct will be shared openly in the form of Open Deliverables. This will be the case of the Citizen Social Science tools, that will be gathered together in a Toolkit (D2.4 Open Citizen Social Science Toolkit) and the teaching materials of the PhD summer school on Citizen Social Science (D8.4 Citizen Social Science Open Training Materials for social scientists PhD programmes). Both deliverables will be public and shared through the CoAct webpage and in public repositories such as Zenodo. Similarly, as soon as possible, the IT application produced during the course of CoAct will be based on open source software and made available under an appropriate open license and publicly available in repositories such as GitHub (see for example D5.3 Open Source digital platform of R&I Action #3).

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/legal_basis/rules_participation/h2020-rules-participation_en.pdf

This frame, though, does not prevent that CoAct will be open to exploitation opportunities, that are also another way to guarantee CoAct sustainability. The main exploitation opportunities, at the time this Deliverable is being prepared (M3) are summarized in Table 8. This does not preclude that others exploitation opportunities may arise during the course of CoAct.

Table 8. CoAct exploitation opportunities and potential partners involved

Opportunity	Explanation	Potential partners involved
Policy services for data-driven decision making by means of citizen social science	With the CoAct Open Citizen Social Science toolkit, interested parties are able to engage in specific consultation services, designing Citizen Social Science projects for societal challenges based on a systematic framework and a network of relevant communities	UB, ZSI, FHP, UNIVIE, UNSAM, OKF
Development of Apps and Digital Platforms	Mobile Apps or crowdsourcing platforms can be designed based or further exploited in cooperation with ICT business partners.	UB, UNSAM, OKF, FARN
Development of inclusive materials to engage vulnerable collectives	CoAct’s inclusive materials could be further adapted to other research methodologies or others collective, based on the expertise of the partners in this field.	UB, UNIVIE, OKF, FSMC, FARN, ZSI, FHP

The main exploitation opportunities foreseen can bus thus divides into 3 categories:

- **Services** for data-driven decision making
- **Digital tools** (Apps and Digital Platform)
- **Materials** to engage vulnerable collectives

9.2 Exploitation Plan Roadmap

The Exploitation Plan will be prepared in agreement with the IP rights frame, as it is defined in the Consortium Agreement. In particular, the CA states that Knowledge generated under the project (“Foreground IP”) will be owned by the partner that generates it. In cased of shared ownership, special rules are agreed.

In order to properly identify, refine and materialize the different CoAct exploitations opportunities, the different actions described hereafter will be implemented.

9.2.1 Identification/refinement of the exploitation opportunities

CoAct is proposing a radically new approach to face four “wicked” social global issues by engaging citizens in a vulnerable situation acting as co-researchers. The approach represents a new understanding of the underexplored field of Citizen Social Science (CSS), understood here as participatory research co-designed and directly driven by citizen groups sharing a social concern. CSS is a very young discipline which is just burgeoning and consequently its exploitation opportunities have not yet been identified. In that sense, CoAct can act as an innovative precursor in order to open up this new field. When looking at the wider Citizen Science field, mainly rooted in Natural Sciences, some successful models can be identified. Two of them are described below.

SPOTTERON

The logo for SPOTTERON, with the word in a bold, blue, sans-serif font. The letter 'O' is replaced by a circular icon containing a stylized human figure with arms raised, similar to the CoAct logo.

SPOTTERON platform is offering Citizen Science projects an adaptable IT solution in order to create their own smartphone apps and interactive maps, including a wide range of features and advanced tools. The users can login at all supported projects with their own user account simultaneously. The business model includes a fixed price model, providing the complete service inclusive design and development of the apps, data management and constant updates and ranging from 4.900 € to 17.450 €.

<https://www.spotteron.net/>

scistarter People-powered science.

The logo for scistarter, with the word 'scistarter' in a bold, blue, sans-serif font and the tagline 'People-powered science.' in a smaller, orange, sans-serif font below it.

Scistarter platform connects Citizen Science volunteers to Citizen Science projects in need of their help. The Citizen Science volunteers have to create an account, which give them access to a personalized dashboard where they can add their interests and location to get custom project and event recommendations. The Citizen Science projects, which as defined as “SciStarter Affiliate”, can gain access to enhanced analytics about their volunteers and perform target search for volunteers based on their location, what instruments they own, or even what skills they have.

Citizen Science volunteers do not need to pay any fee, while Affiliates pay a fee to Access to Premium features.

<https://scistarter.org/>

Although these two business models are conceptually far from the business model CoAct could lead to, they are interesting examples in order to envision future opportunities.

Other options can be considered in relation to small social enterprises such as the one below.

An SME born from the will to tackle societal challenges affecting communities using innovative solutions. The company is focusing on environmental issues affecting citizens, or any other matters of concern, and uses a methodology based on a quadruple helix model of stakeholder engagement (public authorities and policy makers, industries and SMEs, academia, and communities, NGOs and CSOs, amongst others), to promote dialogue, increase transparency, and to co-design innovative solutions that are relevant to all the stakeholders involved. The identified stakeholders are involved in every step of the process: from the co-design of the research question, to the definition and the data gathering strategy, to its validation, analysis and co-design of solutions. Through data gathering and its analysis, new technologies and crowdsourcing, SfC empower communities using a bottom-up approach to co-design local solutions adapted to each local case, while promoting social innovation and the participation of citizens in decision-making processes that affect their quality of life.

<http://scienceforchange.eu/>

The CoAct project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 873048

Mapping for Change works to provide benefit to individuals and communities from disadvantaged or marginalised groups, along with the organisations and networks that support those communities, where the goal is to create positive sustainable transformations in their environment. The company also supports individuals from the aforementioned groups to gain access to higher education at UCL, to study fields connected with our work.

Their Vision: A future in which communities are empowered, sustainable and resilient.

Their Mission: To empower individuals and communities to make a difference to their local area through the use of mapping and geographical information.

Their Aim: To deliver maps and techniques which enable any organisation, group or enterprise to make a change and improve their environments.

<https://mappingforchange.org.uk/>

BE participation: Belgian platform for citizen participation asbl

The Belgian platform for citizen participation is a non-profit association located in Brussels. It aims to stimulate everyone's action in public space. This initiative is the result of a collective reflection on democratic issues, carried out with a shared demand for justice, equality and freedom. The members of the association, all of them involved in civil society, decided to develop a flexible structure, dedicated to the emergence of participatory processes. Like a nursery, BE participation, places its premises and resources at the disposal of projects promising sustainable development and citizen appropriation of the common future. It draws from the field of social innovation to fuel engagement and generate efficient influence on public issues. The platform offers personalized support that makes it easier to anchor the project in the local field: strategic and logistical assistance, mentoring, networking, continuous evaluation.

<https://beparticipation.be/>

During the course of the project, the different exploitation opportunities will be closely monitored, based on the three products identified before (**Services** for data-driven decision making; **Digital tools** such Apps and Digital Platform; **Materials** to engage vulnerable collectives).

9.2.2. Identification of target groups

The first two business models previously cited focused on one unique target market: the promoters of Citizen Science projects. Most often, the promoters of the Citizen Science projects are academic research groups. In many cases, they are lacking of experience in terms of communication and marketing and do not have in-house resources to create and maintain their own IT tools. Spotteron and Scistarter thus provide them both IT solutions and potential volunteers.

As CoAct is focusing on Citizen Social Science, new opportunities can be envisaged. As CoAct will deal with “wicked” social problems and will propose new methodologies for social impact oriented research, new target groups interested by CoAct methodologies/products could be potentially approached:

- 1) Public administrations
- 2) Social enterprises
- 3) Civil Society Organizations

All these groups can be potentially interested by new research methodologies/tools that place the citizens in a vulnerable situation at the centre of the R&I process and that are able to transform scientific results into evidenced based political actions.

These potential target groups will be carefully studied and segmented during the course of CoAct.

9.2.3 Preparation of marketing strategy(ies)

Once the exploitation opportunities and the potential target group carefully identified, the last action in order to prepare the CoAct exploitation plan will deal with the formulation of marketing

strategy(ies) to be implemented. This will constitute a valuable input in order to elaborate a complete Business Plan, to be done by the owner of the IP of the exploitable product.

The marketing strategy will include the following items:

- Identification of target customers (see 1.1.2)
- Prospection of the potential market, also in terms of potential competitors
- Identification of the product differential values
- Pricing and positioning strategy

Annexes

I. CoAct Event List

Activity	Month
Hackatons/ Datathons (WP3, R&I Action Mental Health Care Barcelona)	M6-36
Hackatons/ Datathons (WP4, R&I Action Youth Employment Vienna)	M6-36
Hackatons/ Datathons (WP5, R&I Action Environmental Justice Buenos Aires)	M6-36
Open calls launching events (WP6)	M18
Citizen Social Science Summer School PhD students (WP8)	M21

III. Events template

Events Template									
In the Events Template partners will input the information about the events they host and/or contribute to communicate and disseminate CoAct project and results									
Event title	Date	Location	Description	Target audience	Objective	Approx. assistants	Responsible partner	Host and/or contributor?	Other CoAct partners collaborating

IV. Event list 2020

Event	Attendants	Where and when?	Responsible Partner
Citizen Science Conference	1,000 attendants	EEUU 2021	UB, ZSI, UNIVIE
European Citizen Science Association Conference	600 attendants	EU, 2020, 2022	UB, ZSI, UNIVIE, FHP.
European Forum for Studies of Policies for R&I EUSPRI	200 attendants	EU, yearly	
International conference on social science and humanities	500 attendants	International, yearly	FHP
International Sociological Association	6.000 attendants	International, biennially	FHP
European Sociological Association	5.000 attendants	EU, biennially	FHP
Austrian Citizen Science Conference	300 attendants	National	ZSI, UNIVIE
Conference on Computational Social Science	1,000 attendants	International, yearly	UB
Conference on Complex Systems	1,000 attendants	International, yearly	UB
Euroscience Open Forum ESOF	4,000 attendants	EU, 2020Trieste, 2022TBC	UB
re:publica	9,000 attendants	Berlin, each year	GIG
Sónar+D	6,000 attendants	Barcelona, each year	UB
World Mental Health Day	--	International, yearly	FSMC
Living Knowledge Conference	300 attendants	International, 2021, 2022	UB
Data Justice Conference	200 attendants	International, 2020	UB

V. Editorial Plan

An Editorial Plan is used to control publication of content across different social media. The CoAct's editorial plan is to have a tool where all consortium partners can directly contribute to the posts that we would be sharing through Twitter, Facebook and Instagram. In order to establish a sustainable editorial plan we are introducing two key focal areas:

A) Guideline and Governance

B) Processes and Tools

Step 1

Guideline and Governance - This refers to editorial quality standards, preferred practices and guiding principles that define and distinguish the value of CoAct.

I) *Content tone and voice* – With CoAct we want to adopt a warm and friendly communication voice that will consider simple and insightful language depending on our target groups and their context.

II) *Editorial quality* - Every content input should be judged against the value your audience expects from it. When thinking about the information you want to share consider the following: Is it readable, understandable, actionable and shareable?

Step 2

B) Processes and Tools – How our team collaborates and communicates effectively and identifying tools to get the work done

I) *Collaboration and work flow* - Consortium partners are expected to contribute 3 posts for every two weeks. For GIG to be able to schedule all the posts for the next 2 weeks, partners will have to input their contribution before. E.g. GIG wants to schedule post from Monday April 13th to Friday 24th. In order to do so, partners will have to input their content the latest by Wednesday 8th so that GIG has the next two days to organise and schedule posts.

#8.1 Exploitation, Dissemination and Communication Plan

II) *Tools* - GIG will be in charge of scheduling the post in different social media using a free software for this purpose. Consortium partners will have access to the editorial plan that will be used to get their contributions.

III) *Quality assurance* – GIG will ensure the highest standards of content quality e.g. processes to keep typos, grammatical mistakes, and factual inaccuracies out of the content

Social Media Channels

Consortium Partners are encouraged to create one post per social media channel, meaning, one post for Facebook, Twitter and Instagram, however this also depends on the available information/content that they can share. Each channel has different formats that are shared with partners as a general consideration when inputting their content:

A) Twitter – It has a 280 characters limit. Tweets should be short, concise and clear. A picture and/or link can be attached, but if not, good content will also pop out by itself.

B) Facebook – For Facebook posts we suggest to attach an image and/or link to the content as well as keeping the posts short and with very simple and straightforward language and taking into account CoAct’s communication voice and tone.

C) Instagram - An image will always be needed when posting on instagram since it’s a visual platform. An effective Instagram strategy is storytelling that involves micro-stories that tie the story with CoAct aim and objectives.

CoAct Editorial Plan							
About the Editorial Plan							
The editorial plan is an open and collaborative tool to organise the social media posts with the different consortium partners.							
The Editorial Plan will be a space where partners can directly input the information that GIG requests to communicate and disseminate the CoAct Project through its social media channels.							
The two main social media channels that GIG would use to share and communicate the CoAct! Project are Facebook and Twitter.							
As a general rule of thumbs, GIG will upload posts on week days from 11:00am to 1:00pm cet, preferably on Tuesdays, Wednesdays and/or Thursdays.							
For managing social media posting we will use: http://www.fanpagekarma.com/ for free as a "software donation" to NGOs.							
1st Week / April 1st -April 15th							
Publish Date	Topic/Title	Input Content	Images/link	Keywords	Author	Social Media	Target group
Filled out by GIG							▼
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The CoAct project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 873048